
Achievement Accounting is a Working Method for Selecting the Optimal Production Mix: a Case Study at the General Company for Electrical Industries

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Abstract: Achievement accounting is a part or one of the constraints theory tools that provides information to help improving operational processes by focusing on the weakest restricted resource so as to reach financial and quantitative goals. This information also contributes to maximizing profitability by directing the company's useful resources towards the optimum production mix that achieves the highest profitability, by following the unit achievement margin method, which is somewhat similar to the variable method for determining the contribution margin. However, achievement accounting firstly charges sales with their direct materials costs only, and secondly adopts the method of achievement rate per minute of processing time in the process. Thus, the current study aims to demonstrate achievement accounting, a sophisticated, structured method that works to determine the best production mix and show the role of achievement accounting in diagnosing limitations and manage bottlenecks in a way that contributes to improving performance. One of the most important findings of the study is that the optimum production mix that maximizes profitability is achieved by adopting the method of completion rate per minute of processing time in the process and building timetables for it.

Key words: Achievement Accounting, Theory of Constraints, Production Mix, Operational Decisions, Iraq.

INTRODUCTION

The modern manufacturing environment represented by technical developments and commercial openness of markets has created changing conditions and an accelerating pace that imposed on business organizations to take decisions and follow procedures and steps that are compatible with those changes in a way that ensures them to remain within the circle of global competition as well as to maintain existing customers and work to win other customers by improving quality products, cost reduction and flexibility in delivery.

However, the existence of some human, financial or technological constraints that limit the performance of the organization, which may reach the point of controlling those units and not the other way around. Thus, this promotes the search for contemporary approaches, concepts and methods that focus on achieving the optimal exploitation of the restricted resource to maximize the profitability of a company through what these concepts and methods provide information that enables it to perform its functions and help it making decisions that are consistent with the rapid changes in a competitive business environment. Perhaps the theory of constraints approach and its tool represented by the achievement accounting, with its concepts and methods is capable of providing information that helps increase profitability through determining the most profitable production mix. Accordingly, the research structure consists of the following:

2. GENERAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

This section discusses the problem, importance, objectives, hypothesis, methodology and structure of the research.

2.1. Problem of the research

The research problem stems from the following aspects:

1. Is there an ability to determine the constraint and the restricted resource through operational processes?
2. How can the company's management take a decision on how to exploit the constraint and the restricted resource in the production of each type of the company's products?
3. Does the company determine the production mix in order to maximize profitability according to achievement accounting?

2.2. Importance of the research

The research derives its importance by providing an integrated application framework in improving profitability through the optimal use of the restricted resource without compromising quality using the theory of constraints approach, as well as the reasons for applying this theory represented by the increasing demand for high-quality products and increased competition, which have revealed the need to apply technologies that are consistent with the modern business environment characterized by competition through adopting modern methods in determining the most profitable commodity mix for the unit rather than relying on the traditional methods of analyzing the margins of contribution.

2.3. Objectives of the research

The research aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Clarifying the concept of achievement accounting that emanates from the theory of constraints, and evaluating its effectiveness as a sophisticated tool in providing appropriate information to assist management in rationalizing restricted production decisions.
2. Clarify the role of achievement accounting through the application of the achievement margin method for the unit and the method of achievement margin for each minute of processing time in the production process and in a manner that contributes to managing the entry, the restricted resource

2.4. Hypothesis of the research

The research assumes that adopting the theory of constraints by employing achievement accounting contributes to achieving the optimal use of the resource to determine the productive mix that maximizes profitability of the economic unit.

2.5. Methods of the research

The research focuses on the inductive approach based on the writings related to the study literature and the analytical approach based on the data collected from the General Company for Electrical Industries (GCEI). This company is one of the companies specialized in electrical industries which is affiliated to the Ministry of Industry and Minerals in Iraq.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

This section discusses concept, principles, objectives and tools of theory of constraints, as follows:

3.1. Theory of constraints evolution

The theory of constraints (TOC) has gone through multiple development phases:

Phase I: The seventies where Goldratt was presented his resolution, known as Optimized Production Technology (OPT) to encounter the causes of resource constraints that hinder the increase in production to meet customer demands.

Phase II: The eighties when Goldratt introduced his book entitled "The Goal" to avoid the main problem with the program OPT which is represented by how to schedule the production and lay down the rules of the theory of constraints.

Phase III: The nineties in which a system to measure performance was used in order to providing operational and financial standards. During that time period, Goldratt published a book called "It's not luck". In fact, this book was a road map for solving problems and providing alternative solutions, (Zeynep, 2014, 931).

3.2. Theory of constraint concept

The theory of constraints is unique in its work as a management tool through which constraints imposed on it are dealt with. A constraint is defined as any factor limiting or preventing the acquisition of more than we want, as organizations or individuals face at least one constraint (Garrison, 2015: 547). Three types of constraints facing the organization can be identified. They are: physical constraints represented in machinery, labor, capacity of the work or production line, lack of materials, area and quality; managerial constraints represented by policy, measurements and mentalities that impede the development of work; and finally, constraints of a special type called bottlenecks that are associated with a lack of process capacity. These are defined as any resource whose available capacity limits the organization's ability to achieve the size of a product or service, product mix, or volatile requirements) Krajewski, 2013, 264).

Traditionally, a company's performance is adversely affected by its constraints. The theory of constraints concept outlines two important things: a- Each system must have at least one constraint and b- The existence of constraints represents opportunities to create improvement.

Constraints determine system performance, so high system constraints will improve performance. The theory of constraints is a qualitative approach that focuses on continuous improvement and systematic research to study and analyze complex problems through thought processes (TP). In addition, TOC has new performance measures that are completely different from traditional cost accounting systems (Rahman, 2016, 337). Theory of constraints were defined as a set of methods used to maximize the operational income when operations face areas that represent asphyxiation and others that do not represent asphyxiation (Horngren, 2015, 441). It also was defined as a management philosophy that is concerned with identifying the constraints that limit the company's work optimally, and works to weaken the strength of these constraints by supporting logistical processes, thinking processes and performance indicators that differ from the traditional management philosophy aiming at increasing profitability and reducing costs to improve organizational performance (Diego, 2014: 333).

3.3. Theory of constraints principles

Hamilton, (2009: 18) discussed the principles on which the theory of constraints is based on as follows:

1. Focusing on flow rather than on balancing energies
2. The lack of symmetry of utility and effectiveness of resources.
3. The time margin attained at the level of resources achieved equals the increase in the rate of outputs of restricted resources.
4. The time margin achieved at the level of unrestricted resources is equal.
5. The transfer batch is not equal to the production batch.
6. The production batch must be unstable (variable).
7. Focusing on synchronous flow instead of focusing on energies.

8. The effect of any capital investment on total productivity, inventory and operating expenses should be considered.

3.4. *Theory of Constraints assumptions*

Horngren (2015, 441) explained the assumptions related to the theory of constraints. They are as follows:

1. Using the margin of achievement: maximizing profitability requires attaining the highest level of achievement and this is done by converting the raw materials into sales. So, the margin of achievement is expressed with the money that enters the organization minus what is paid to the suppliers. This can be calculated by subtracting the variable cost of raw materials used in production from the sales revenue.
2. The direct labor costs, at least in the short term, are fixed costs.
3. There is at least one constraint in each system or work area that motivates the working personnel to take measures to increase the efficiency and energy of the operation process.
4. Focusing on managing constraints rather than reducing costs is an opportunity to create improvement.
5. Dividing the resources in terms of bottlenecks into the following three resources as pointed out by (Wolniak, 2018, 2):
 - a) A resource that represent a minor choke point in the production process.
 - b) A resource that represents multiple bottlenecks in the production process.
 - c) A resource that represents constraints on energy.

Here it is necessary to understand the behavior of the bottleneck during a specific time period depending on the nature of the production system being analyzed.

3.5. *Theory of constraints benefits*

Michal & Iveta (2010, 74) and Davood (2015:39) indicated the most important benefits of applying the theory of constraints as follows:

1. The possibility of increasing productivity in a form that maximizes profitability in the light of making some simple changes in operational processes.
2. It is considered good tools that encourage the work in the spirit of the team in different areas of the organization's work.
3. Theory of constraints is considered good processes that drive towards the beginning efforts of improvement. It also provides benefits in an immediate and tangible form.
4. It allows the growth cycle of capital and productivity without the need for an additional period or staff.
5. It provides methods for evaluating the correct values of changes from which the organization benefits in selecting the best alternatives leading to the right behavior and decisions (Michal & Iveta, 2010, 74).
6. It helps as a mechanism for adjusting and scheduling production (Davood, 2015, 39).

3.6. *Steps for applying the theory of constraints*

James, (2010, 213) pointed out the five focus steps (FS 5). These steps introduced a set of rules and procedures that determine how to manage the process in a form indicating to improve the productivity of a specific task or the process as a whole.

The first three steps have a direct effect on the overall dynamic balance process of the procedure and then convert to the overall dynamic balance of the simplified procedure, which is widely used to achieve rapid benefits in the short term, which are represented in:

1. Determining the system constraints.
2. Making a decision on how to take advantage of the system's constraint.
3. Appending everything else to the above decision The long-term steps (4 and 5) provide a platform for developing a growth chart associated with stability:
4. Lift the system constraint.
5. Refer to step (1) if the constraint is broken (overcome) in any of the previous steps.

3.7. Theory of constraints tools:

There is a set of tools used by companies to define and address the constraints that they suffer from their various types which work on reducing or eliminating problems that hinder their ability to achieve goals.

1. Mechanism for monitoring and scheduling production: The DBR methodology is considered one of the tools that support the mechanism of constraints theory. By developing the DBR methodology, it is no longer limited to dealing with manufacturing problems only, but also based on finding solutions to problems within operational processes by setting an appropriate flowchart to flow inventory within operational processes and avoiding inventory accumulation at any stage which helps to improve efficiency, cost and time by working to achieve a balance between the speed with which the constrained resources operate and the timing of the use of inventory and making use of available capacity and obtain the maximum possible benefit (Manaf, 2015, 10).
2. Thinking process (TP): It is a method used to solve bottlenecks and develop processes by defining, weakening, and removing one or more determinants by adopting the cause-and-effect principle.

The easiest, most effective, and efficient way is to focus on the modest problem that falls within the core problem so that decision-making or change and the effect of the decision taken on both costs and profits through the creation of a set of logical reasoning tools that can be used to answer problems and put forward appropriate solutions (James, 2010: 747).

3. Achievement Accounting (AA): It appeared in the nineties within the writings of Goldratt as one of the constraints theory tools to present a new vision through a set of measures and the introduction of an approach focused on interest in managing the constraints imposed on the production processes of the organization and its work is considered complementary to the management system by providing the necessary information that helps to manage constraints and control it to achieve continuous improvement and maximize achievement (Elsukova, 2015, 84).

3.8. Achievement accounting and its role to rationalize operational decisions

3.8.1. The concept of achievement accounting

Achievement accounting is defined as a managerial tool that seeks to maximize the return on the constrained resource and helps to define the variety of products based on market demand (Anwarul, 2015, 19). It is also defined as an alternative approach that differs from the traditional approach to measuring cost and benefit. Its main goal is to remove the constraints that hinder the growth of production, sales, and cash flow, in order to obtain the largest profit margin (Andrei, 2015, 225). Moreover, it is defined as one of the ways that support decision-making and aims to increase the profitability of the company by identifying the determinants that hinder the ability of the organization's resources to achieve its goals and focus on simple measures that guide behavior in work areas toward organizational goals. Achievement accounting includes three basic concepts or measures of application represented in achievement, operating expenses, and inventory (asset).

1. Achievement: It defines the rate at which the system generates money, the amount of products or services that can be produced and sold in a given period, and it is measured by deducting direct materials from sales revenue.
2. Operating expenses: They are all costs that contributed to attaining the achievement, which is the cost of manufacturing, except the costs of direct materials. Direct wages are within operating expenses and are considered fixed costs (DRAŽIĆ, 2018: 1385).
3. Inventory (asset): The concept of assets in achievement accounting does not differ from the concept in conventional accounting except for inventory, where it is defined as the money that is spent on things with the intention of converting into achievement. In general, the inventory which did not contribute to attaining the achievement is valued at the cost of the materials only, unlike the traditional approach that charges the inventory with part or all of the operating expenses.

3.8.2. *The principles underpinning achievement accounting*

The basic principles of achievement accounting discussed by (Elsukova, 2025, 48) are summarized as follows:

1. The value of the product or service is realized at the moment of sale.
2. The principle of redistributing resources in places with bottlenecks in order to maximize the outputs.
3. The principle of urgent necessity
4. The principle of comparison between approaches of costing account.
5. The principle of unity or integration.
6. The principle of continuous improvement of unit systems.

3.8.3. *The assumptions underlying the achievement accounting*

Parkhi et. al., (2015, 5) and) Suaad, 2021, 4 (indicated a set of assumptions that underlies achievement accounting. These are summarized as follows:

1. According to the achievement accounting, the focus is on managing constraints and bottlenecks and supporting operational decisions in the short and medium term because the ability to generate fund is restricted.
2. Operating costs in the short term can be considered as period costs, since they do not change in proportion to the level of activity and the greater part of them is fixed, therefore it is not allocated among products as the goal of decision makers is to reduce operating costs.
3. According to the achievement accounting, the direct materials cost is affected by the size and variety of products, as it is a single variable cost component and therefore is considered a basis for developing internal reports for the purposes of rationalizing the decision-making process.
4. Maximizing the overall goal of the organization is made by increasing sales to the maximum extent possible, then reducing inventory levels and investments to a minimum without affecting the productivity goal.

3.8.3. *Requirements for implementing achievement accounting*

To implement the achievement accounting approach, Al-Ashmawi (2011: 369) pointed out a number of main fundamentals that must be provided. These are discussed as follows:

1. Division of the structure of manufacturing cost items within the parameters of the modern manufacturing environment.

2. Determination of the production process obstacles, as the time is one of the factors that affect the measurement of achievement margin. Therefore, the constraints that would increase that time should be removed.
3. Taking care of time management is one of the ruling elements in measuring the percentage of achievement and charging indirect manufacturing costs to production within the framework of the achievement accounting approach. The achievement time includes operating time, examination, the transition between production departments and waiting for storage time (reducing the manufacturing cycle time). However, it also excludes all sources of loss that affect achievement.

The sources of loss mentioned by Stephen (2010, 69) are summarized as follows:

Defective: Errors occur in the operational process

Inventory: The creation of surplus of raw materials, work in process and finished goods inventories

Movement: that is, unnecessary movements of workers or machines before, after or during manufacturing

Excess processing: unnecessary time of use and processing that does not add value.

Excess production: It is to provide and produce more products than required quantities.

Transportation: It is the movement of unnecessary and redundant materials or parts within the production line, inventory or other field.

Waiting: It is the waiting time for materials or parts in the processing queue as well as checking and shipping.

4. Product selection decisions in light of achievement accounting

The process of making any decision is considered one of the main tasks performed by the management of any organization. Making decisions to determine the mix of products in light of the limited resources represents a challenge for the management of the organization.

It is undeniable that the traditional methods helped the management to provide practical measures in terms of cost and efficiency. However, technological developments reduced the role of these measures as they focused on unit cost without looking at important aspects of the work environment and the costs committed and the related limitations of possibilities that lead to bottlenecks. Companies today are facing outdated solutions as a result of their application of traditional costing methods (Utku et al, 2011:318). Cost accounting determines the cost of the product according to different methods.

Since the product cost is a key factor used in making the decision to choose the production mix, so the manufacturing performance may be affected. Also, the emergence of control systems in manufacturing processes such as just- in- time production and the theory of constraints contributed to the emergence of accounting methods to determine the cost differently, such as backflush and achievement accounting that focus on restrictions to achieve the highest profitability of the product (Wilks & Burks, 2008:355).

Achievement accounting is a great approach to reach the right solution by understanding how to manage a constraint in order to help the management take decisions at various organizational levels, whether they are decisions of a long-term strategic nature or decisions of an operational or tactical nature such as decisions to add a new product, cancel a product, closing a factory, using resources, selling or moving to additional processing, accepting or rejecting private sales orders, etc. (Steven: 2007: 59)

Decisions, whether short-term or long-term, depend on the differential analysis that represents the difference between cash inflow and cash outflow and related to different alternatives. Lal, (2008:

9.1) believes that decisions are classified according to certain bases from the perspective of time into:

1. Short-term decisions regarding operational costs.
2. Long-term capital budgeting decisions.

Also, Hansen (2006: 782) indicates that from a functional point of view, decisions are classified to two types, as follows:

1. Strategic decisions related to the strategic objectives of the organization
2. Operational (tactical) decisions related to work of a limited or narrow scope that perform a major purpose related to the strategic objective of the company.

The company faces limitations or constraints when the ability to manufacture a product or provide a service is determined in some way. In addition, decisions to make use of resources in determining the production mix among a number of products and giving each product a specific percentage within the process require an analysis of how to know the best way to exploit the available resources for limited supplies that are represented in a material or a scarce element used in manufacturing the product. This is mostly related to the time required to manufacture the product or render the service, or related to space (Sawyers, 2013:184).

There are a number of traditional methods in cost accounting to determine the product mix from the oldest. All costs are tracked and charged to the product and the evaluation is conducted on the basis of absolute or relative profit. The profitability of the product is examined against the total cost as the decision maker chooses the most profitable products.

There is an alternative or another traditional method that depends on allocating the restricted resource on products according to the contribution margins of the products after subtracting the variable cost of sales divided by the restricted element (an operating hour) and arranging them according to their preference (Olli & Weidong, 2016: 222).

Vinicius (2013: 4) indicates that in order to choose the best production mix by means of achievement accounting, which emanates from the theory of constraints, there are two steps must be followed:

- 1- Determining the unique obstacle, represented by the productive resource because the energy available for the resource is smaller than the demand capacity.
- 2- Determining the optimal use of the resource and not waste any time or productivity as a result of inefficiency in the exploitation of the resource to maximize profitability according to the achievement approach. This is done by managing the constraint and how to achieve the greatest amount of achievement by using the rate of achievement of the dollar per minute and for each scheduled production job as well as rearranging production priorities according to the highest achievement rate per minute for products. Therefore, the production that produces the highest margin must come first with priorities production scheduling (Steven, 2007: 60).

Moreover, Krajewski (2013: 264) confirms that the exploitation of restricted resources to identify the best productive mix according to the theory of constraints approach is determined through:

1. Determining the best mixture according to the dollar's achievement margin for each hour/minute of processing time of the restricted resource (constraint), and the priority is determined with the highest return.
2. Allocating the restricted resource on the products in light of the achievement rate.

4.2. Decisions to choose the product range in light of achievement accounting:

A company faces limitations or constraints when the ability is determined in some way to manufacture a product or provide a service. Decisions to take advantage of resources in determining the production mix among a number of products and giving each product a specific

percentage within the process require an analysis of how to know the best way to exploit the available resources with respect to the limited supplies that are represented in a rare item or element used in manufacturing the product mostly related to the time required to manufacture the product or render the service, or related to space (Sawyers, 2013: 184).

In order to make the appropriate decision regarding the exploitation of resources through differentiation (products' contribution margins analysis) in production, products are definitely chosen on the basis of achieving the highest profit margin. This can provide an idea of the production mix that maximizes profitability (Al-Takriti, 2010: 173).

The decisions usually take a hierarchy according to the organizational levels of the organization. Senior management is mainly concerned with decisions of a long-term strategic nature. In contrast, short-term decisions are of an operational or tactical nature that are of interest to the middle management and whose effects extend for a short period. Examples of short-term decisions are: to exploit resources, sell or move to additional processing, accept or reject other sales orders, etc. (Al-Fadagh, 2013: 40).

Moreover, whether the decisions are short-term or long-term depend on the differential analysis that represents the difference between cash inflows and cash outflows related to the different alternatives. Decisions are classified according to certain bases from a time perspective into two types (Lal, 2008: 9.1):

- a) Short-term decisions related to operational costs.
- b) Long-term decisions related to capital budgets. From the perspective of evaluation of decisions, they are divided into two types (Salem, 2009: 182).
 - a) Planned decisions, i. e., available periodically.
 - b) Unplanned decisions taken to address a special case or a specific problem.

From a functional perspective, decisions are of two types:

- a) Strategic decisions related to the strategic goals of the organization (Hansen, 2006: 782)
- b) Operational (tactical) decisions related to businesses with a more limited and narrow scope that performs a large purpose related to the strategic goal of the company. The process of making an operational decision must go through five steps: -
 1. Define the problem with a focus on the goal to be accomplished
 2. Identify available alternatives as possible solutions to the problem, and neglecting impractical alternatives.
 3. Identify all the expected benefits associated with each practical alternative.
 4. Compare the costs and benefits related to each alternative, and how closely the alternative relates to the overall objectives of the organization.
 5. Choose the most beneficial alternative that maximizes the overall goal of the organization.

4.3. Decisions to choose the product range in light of achievement accounting

A company faces limitations or constraints when its ability is restricted in some way to manufacture a product or render a service. Decisions to take advantage of resources in determining the production mix between a number of products and giving each product a specific percentage within the process require an analysis of how to know the best way to exploit the available resources with respect to the limited supplies that are represented in a scarce material or component used in manufacturing a product. This is mostly related to the time required to manufacture the product or render the service, or related to space (Sawyers, 2013: 184).

The decisions for profitability planning and determining the production mix are based on measuring the cost of each product and setting the selling price, after which the focus is on the

products that achieve the highest profitability during sales and marketing. Mou'amneh, (2004: 113) indicated that the optimal production mix is traditionally determined under limited resources according to the following bases or assumptions:

1. The relative importance of available resources is equal.
2. The contribution of each product to cover its fixed costs is focused on.
3. The achievement volume as a result of the stability of resource capacity is limited.

Al-Yamour (2010: 417) confirmed that determining the best level of product diversification traditionally depends on how much each product contributes to containing fixed costs and hence the priority in production comes regardless of the constraints imposed.

Improvement of profitability requires identifying the correct set of requests. This requires utilizing constrained resources to determine the best production mix according to the theory of constraints approach. This is determined according to the view of (Krajewski (2013: 264) by the following:

- a) Determine the best mix according to the achievement margin of the dollar per hour / minute of the processing time of the constrained resource, and the preference is determined by the highest return.
- b) The constrained resource is allocated to the products in light of the achievement rate.

5. PRACTICAL PART OF THE RESEARCH

5.1. Research Company Profile

The General Company for Electrical Industries was established in 1967. At the end of 2015, Al-Ezz General Company was merged with the General Company for Electrical Industries to complete the structures and rules necessary for electrical and electronic production of various types because of the elements of success of Al-Ezz Company by the form of the electronic physical and technical rules. After the merger of the two companies the name of the company has become the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries.

The company consists of a number of factories distributed over three geographical sites: Al-Waziriya factories; Al-Taji Lamps Factories; Al-Ezz Factories in Al-Taji and the Furniture Factory in Baghdad.

With the aim of proving the research hypothesis and explaining the role of achievement accounting as a tool that depends on the theory of constraints approach in achieving the optimal exploitation of the constrained resource to maximize the achievement margin to be reflected on the outputs and thus enables the management to rationalize the decisions of the optimal production mix of products, the electric heater products with a capacity of 120 liters; 80 liters and 40 liters manufactured at Al- Waziriya site were chosen.

5.2. Implementation steps for achievement accounting:

For the purpose of implementing achievement accounting steps the following steps are required to be followed:

First: Cost structure analysis The General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries adopts the volume of activity or production as a measure of capacity in one of its factories located in Al-Waziriya. This factory produces electric heaters of varying capacities 120 liters, 80 liters and 40 liters.

According to the achievement accounting approach the costs structure is as follows:
1- *Variable costs*: In light of achievement accounting, production is charged with the cost of direct materials only and other indirect materials are considered fixed costs (period costs). Table (1) shows components for each product.

Table 1. Cost of raw materials used in manufacturing electric heater products

No.	Item Name	120-liters heater	80-liters heater	40- liter heater
1	Tank cover	8631	8631	7050
2	Tank body	2 1 868	13987	6980
3	Base	1847	1754	----
4	Heater cover	1593	1593	1200
6	Socket	911	911	91 0
7	Frame	9 06	580	42 0
8	Upper cover	5022	5022	4 920
9	Lower cover	5022	5022	4 920
	Total direct material	4 5 8 00	375 00	26400
10	Nylon cover	34	34	34
11	Cable	1500	1500	1500
12	Pipe	736	736	736
13	Welding wire	815	815	552
14	Thread seal tape	74	74	74
18	Glass wall	4496	4496	1 250
19	Tapping screw	372	372	496
20	Plug DIN	300	300	300
21	Rivet	135	135	105
22	Heater with thermostat	13 000	13 000	13 000
23	Lead wire metal	130	130	130
24	Pilot light	105	105	105
25	Label (outer)	50	50	50
26	Label (inner)	50	50	50
27	3/4 inch reversing connection	400	400	400
28	Terminal	50	50	---
29	Nylon case	1000	1000	500
30	Bice	3000	1800	450
31	Coloring	7 33	333	12
32	Label	100	100	100
33	Socket	1520	1520	1086
34	Thermometer	---	---	250
35	Breaked	---	---	100
36	Bolt, Nut , Washer	---	---	120
	Total cost of indirect materials	28 6 00	27000	2 1 4 00
	Total cost of materials	74400	64500	47800

2- *Operating expenses*: The direct costs of materials are charged to the cost of goods sold and the inventory. While, the other costs (indirect materials, direct wages and indirect manufacturing expenses) are considered as period (fixed) costs charged to the period in which they are incurred and not charged to production. These costs are accounted for 13% of the total costs of raw materials, which represent 9,700 dinars for a 120-liter product, 8,400 dinars for a 80-liter product and 6200 dinars for a 40-liter product.

Second: Determination of the constraints

As it has been mentioned earlier, the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries manufactures a heater product of varying capacities 120, 80 and 40 liters. These products are

manufactured and assembled in seven operations or work stations. Each production process has one technical worker and one job.

To determine the constraints of the process (bottleneck), the technological path is required to be tracked and the available capacity for the resource and the time spent in each process or station are specified as shown in Table (2).

Table 2. The time required for each product according to the technological track (minutes)

Product (Heater)	Chipping	Perforation	Rolling mill	Welding	Plastic injection	Coloring / dyeing	Final assembly	Total
120-Liters	18 m.	26 m.	15 m.	24 m.	10 m.	15 m.	18 m.	126 m.
80-Liters	17 m.	20 m.	15 m.	21 m.	10 m.	15 m.	18 m.	116 m.
40 – Liters	13 m.	12 m.	10 m.	13 m.	8 m.	10 m.	25 m.	91 m.

Third: Time Management:

The company usually aims to maximize profitability and meet the best possible weekly demand for the products, which are (40 units with a capacity of 120 liters, 60 units with a capacity of 80 liters and 20 units with a capacity of 40 liters). The available time weekly for the three products after excluding the normal lost time is 2,360 minutes. By multiplying the processing time in each process of a particular product by the number of units required per week, we get the time required for production in each process and then adding the required times across the products and through each process we reach the total time of a process, and then compared that to the time available to determine the constraint as shown in Table (3) below.

Table 3. Determining available resources' utilization ratios to identify bottlenecks.

The process	120-Liters Product	80-Liters product	40-liters product	Time required	available time	Percentage
Chipping	720	1020	260	2,000	2360	% 85
Perforation	1040	1200	240	2480	2360	105%
Rolling	600	900	200	1700	2360	72%
Welding	960	1260	260	2,480	2360	105%
Plastic injection	400	600	160	1,160	2360	50%
Coloring	600	900	200	1,700	2360	72%
Final assembly	720	1080	500	2,300	2360	97%

As shown in Table (3), it is clear that the constrained resource representing the bottleneck is determined by the difference between the time required and the time available for each process across the products, which is:

- a) Perforation process, the available time was insufficient to complete the production mixture or to meet the demand, where it amounted to 240 minutes.
- b) The welding process, the available time was insufficient to complete the production mixture or to fulfill the demand, where it amounted to 240 minutes.

5.3. The decision to choose a production mix

Usually, within the case study company many operational decisions are repeatedly made. The most important of which is the decision to determine the production mix among a number of products and give each product a specific percentage within the production process. This is done by a manager who has been granted powers and responsibilities and in cooperation with the cost department without conducting a study and scientific analysis, where the decision is made based the highest margin of contribution or higher sales of the product. In light of using achievement accounting, the decision is made as follows:

5-3-1-Decision point: Determining the production mix according to the achievement rate method for each product.

a) The achievement rate for each of the products was calculated, as shown in Table (4).

Table 4. The data related to the products manufactured and their volumes of demand.

Product (Heater)	Weekly order volume	Unit sale price	Unit variable cost	Unit contribution margin	Product rank
120-Liters	40	120,000	45,800	74,200	1
80 –Liters	60	107,000	37,500	69,500	2
40 -Liters	20	75,000	26,400	48,600	3

When arranging the products from the highest to the lowest, the sequence of products was based on the contribution margin for each product, which were the 120-leters heater, the 80-leters heater and the 40-leters heater respectively. These ranks were identical to the company's arrangement. For the purpose of reaching the achievement rate for each product, the achievement margin for each product was divided by the time required to produce a unit. These calculations are shown in Table (5).

Table 5. Achievement rate for each product

Product (Heater)	Achievement margin	Time required for the product	Achievement rate	Arrangement
120-Liters	74,200	126 minutes	589 m. / unit	2
80-Liters	69,500	116 minutes	599 m. / unit	1
40-Liters	48,600	91 minutes	506 m. / unit	3

b) The constrained resource in each production process is allocated to the products according to the order established in Table (1).

It was found that there was no constraint or restriction in each of the process of cutting, rolling, plastic injection, dyeing, and assembly which the products go through, as the available

Table 6. Determination of the product mix

Product (Heater)	Weekly demand for the product	Constraint time required for each production process		Available power (minute)	The production mix (the sales)
		Perforation	Welding		
80-Liters	60 units	1,200	1,260	2,360	60
120- Liters	40 units	1,040	960	2,360	40
40-Liters	20 units	120	140		10

time is 2,360 minutes weekly in each production stage. This is sufficient to meet the production requirements. However, the constraint lies in each of the drilling and welding processes, amounting to 240 minutes in both processes, as in Table (3) to complete the production mix. Based on the achievement rate, the constrained resource was allocated towards the 80-leters heater, then the 120-leters heater, finally to 40-leters heater, as shown in Table (6).

Accordingly, the best production mix is to produce 60 units of the 80-leters heater, 40 units of the 120-leters heater and 10 units of the 40-leters heater.

3- Calculation of profitability of the selected production mix and the return on investment:

Table 7. Determining profitability of the production mix on the basis of the unit's achievement rate.

Profits	
Income	$(\$107,000 \times 10) + (\$120,000 \times 40) + (\$75,000 \times 10) = 11,970,000$
Variable costs:	
Direct materials:	$(\$37,500 \times 60) + (\$45,800 \times 40) + (\$26,400 \times 10) = (4,346,000)$
Achievement margin:	7,624,000
Operating expenses:	$(\$35,400 \times 60) + (\$38,300 \times 40) + (\$27,600 \times 10) = (3,932,000)$
Net profit:	<u>3,692,000</u>
Investments:	15,100,000
Return on investment:	% 24

Therefore, the optimal plan according to the achievement rate method for the unit produced was that achieved the maximum profitability represented by accepting the production of 60 units of the 80-leters heater, 40 units of the 120-leters heater and 10 units of the 40-leters heater.

5.3.2. Decision point: Determining the best production mix in light of applying the theory of constraints (achievement accounting) according to the following:

a) Calculating the achievement rate per minute of processing time in the process.

It is clear from Table (8) that the arrangement of products according to their preference is first the 40-leters heater, then the 80-leters heater and the remainder of the constrained resource is used in the production of the product 120-leters heater, to maximize its utilization while achieving the maximum possible commitment to customers and this is done through the formation of a timetable that shows maximizing productivity of the constrained resource.

Table 8. Achievement rate per minute in the restricted resource

Product (Heater)	120-leters heater	80-leters heater	40-leters heater
Demand in units	40	60	20
Selling price	\$120,000	\$107,000	\$75,000
Variable cost	\$45,800	\$37,500	\$26,400
Achievement margin per unit	\$74,200	\$69,500	\$46,100
Time at the bottleneck	50 m.	41 m.	25 m.
Achievement rate per minute	\$1,614	\$1,655	\$1,944

b) Allocation of the constrained resource to the products according to their preference, step 1. As can be seen in table (9) above, the decision point in determining the optimum production mix was to produce 20 units of the 40-leters heater, 60 units of the 80-leters heater, and 35 units of the 120-leters heater.

Table (9): Dretermining the product mix

Center of Operation	Available Time (minutes)	Minutes remaining after making 20 units of 40-leters heater	Minutes remaining after making 60 units of 80-leters heater	35 units of of the 120-leters heater can be made
Chipping	2,360	2,100 minutes	1,080 minutes	450 minutes
Perforation	2,360	2,120 minutes	920 minutes	0
Rolling mill	2,360	2,160 minutes	1,260 minutes	735 minutes
Welding	2,360	2,100 minutes	840 minutes	0
Plastic injection	2,360	2,200 minutes	1,600 minutes	1,250 minutes
The dye	2,360	2,160 minutes	1,260 minutes	735 minutes
Final polishing	2,360	1,860 minutes	1,080 minutes	450 minutes

It is clear from these results that there was no restriction or constraint in a number of production processes such as cutting, rolling, plastic injection, dyeing and assembly. So, each one did not represent a constrained resource, and in turn each of them was used for less than its available capacity.

Moreover, commitment to delivery to customers indicated that the perforation and welding stages were loaded with a capacity of 105% of its capacity, meaning that the constraint can be in the two stages according to the achievement rate, dinar per hour or the minute at processing time. Therefore, the focus was on increasing the achievement of the constrained resource by scheduling the constraint in a form that maximizes output and it contributes to reducing operating expenses as well as the speedy response to customer orders. All of these leave a positive impact on financial measures such as net profit and cash flow.

c) Calculating the profitability of the selected production mix and the return on investment

Table 10. Profitability of the selected products based on the rate of achievement per minute

Profits	
Income:	$(\$120,000 \times 35) + (\$107,000 \times 60) + (\$75,000 \times 20) = \$12,120,000$
Direct materials:	$(\$45,800 \times 35) + (\$37,500 \times 60) + (\$26,400 \times 20) = \underline{(4,381,000)}$
Achievement margin:	7,739,000
operating expenses:	$(\$38,300 \times 35) + (\$35,400 \times 60) + (\$27,600 \times 20) = \underline{(4,016,500)}$
Net profit:	<u>3,722,500</u>
Investments:	15,100,000
Return on investment:	25%

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research found a number of conclusions and suggested some recommendations.

5.1. Conclusions

The most important conclusions reached in the research are as follows:

1. Adoption of the concept of achievement accounting through the theory of constraints contributes to supporting management activities in planning, decision-making and cost control by focusing on achievement and reducing inventory rates.

2. The information provided by achievement accounting is one of the tools of the theory of constraints that helps to make decisions having a positive impact on the profitability of the company.
3. Using the hourly or minute achievement rate method, depending on the processing time schedule, to determine the most profitable production mix, achieves the possibility for the economic unit to link the achievement and time spent in accomplishing achievement and identify the untapped capacity of unconstrained resources through production stages.
4. The high percentages of operating expenses amounting to 46% of the 120-liter heater, 49% of the 80-liter heater and 51% of 40-liter heater of the total cost of the product affected the achievement rate and net profit and return on investment. This was due to the length of the product life cycle that was not appropriate for the contemporary competitive business environment.
5. The General Company for Electrical Industries did not adopt the contemporary management accounting approaches and techniques that contribute to determining the most profitable product range under the determinants as well as techniques for allocating indirect manufacturing costs.
6. Uses of the restricted resource on the basis of products' contribution margins did not contribute to maximizing the profitability of the company.

5.2. Recommendations

The research suggested the following important recommendations:

1. Applying achievement accounting as one of the constraints theory tools because of its role in providing information that helps to raise the efficiency of performing production operations to determine the optimal production mix that maximizes the company's profitability.
2. Using timetables for the purpose of reconsidering the time spent on the activity of the constrained resource in order to reduce the time required for the production of a single unit. This can be done through process redesign or process re-engineering and investing in new machines or working overtime.
3. The necessity of restructuring the productive capacity in order to balance the capacities of the production stages, where there is an excess time in four production operations according to the theory constraints approach.
4. Redesigning the product in a way that is in line with the international companies' view in which their products are designed on the basis of shortening the product life cycle to reduce operating expenses.
5. The General Company for Electrical Industries should adopt Activity-Based Costing (ABC) technique in determining the cost and profitability of the production line, as it assists the management in determining activities that do not add value, reduce processing time, cancel or merge activities that do not add value to reduce their costs.

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